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Index of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CVE - Counter-violent extremism

CPDSI - Centre de prévention des dérives sectaires liées à l'Islam

DDR - Disarmament, demobilisation and reintegration

DPKO - United Nations Department of Peacekeeping Operations

P/CVE - Prevention/Contering-Violent Extremism

RAN - Radicalisation Awareness Network

UK - United Kingdom

UN - United Nations

Executive summary

The current report is part of the WayOut - “Integrated Exit Programme for Prison and Probation” projects’ Work Package 2 - state of art analysis. It aims to review deradicalisation literature, exploring the theoretical and practical developments in this field. With a threefold structure, the report starts with an introduction where a conceptual distinction of key terms (e.g., deradicalisation, disengagement, counter-violent extremism, counter radicalisation) is made and a definition of exit programmes is presented. After, micro (individual), meso (group level) and macro (societal) determinants of radicalisation are explored and synthesized, contributing to our understanding of radicalisation processes. In this section, an emphasis is given to models of (de)radicalisation in the prison context.

The second part of the report explores the theoretical and practical developments on exit programmes. Namely, this section draws attention to theories that can help researchers understand disengagement and deradicalisation processes, in order to develop better intervention programmes. First, some barriers to deradicalisation are presented, followed by the pull/push factors framework, highlighting deradicalisation factors. Then, studies presenting disengagement and deradicalisation factors are put forth. Additionally, a more theoretical approach is also developed, with an explanation of psychological theories, such as the investment model, cognitive dissonance theory, reactance theory, self-categorisation theory and social identity theory, since these represent important models to understand deradicalisation, as well as theories from other research fields. Moreover, this section describes the goals of exit programmes (i.e., deradicalise, disengage, rehabilitate and reintegrate) and main pillars of various programmes (e.g., reinterpretation of ideology; social service; individual counselling/psychological component), presenting a brief exploration of the history of these programmes and its implementation in different regions.

The conclusion section draws attention to the main results from this literature review report, making a clear distinction of key terms, providing guidelines on exit programmes’ goals and possible structure, and reflecting on the main factors that promote deradicalisation and disengagement.

1. Introduction

The current report is part of Work Package 2 of WayOut - Integrated Exit Programme for Prison and Probation project and is closely linked with the first goal stated in the project application, that is “to provide a detailed account of the current state of the art in deradicalisation research and other relevant disciplines related to desistance and rehabilitation”. This topic is a relevant one considering that existing research recognises that a lot is still unknown when it comes to understanding the experiences of those who want to leave extremist organisations and the barriers they face in the process (Choudhury, 2009) as well as the quality of the programmes that have been designed and applied for the purpose of helping people leave these organisations/movements (Bovenkerk, 2011).

This state-of-the-art report has the following goals:

- To present a definition of deradicalisation, separating it from similar concepts found in the literature: counter-radicalisation; counter-violent extremist; disarmament; demobilisation and reintegration; disengagement; and exit programmes;
- Provide an up-to-date overview of the theoretical and practical literature on exit programmes.

With these aims, the current report is structured as follows: a conceptual distinction of key terms in the field of deradicalisation is made in section 1.1; an overview on the determinants of radicalisation is presented in section 1.2; then, theoretical and practical developments on exit programmes are explored in section 2, considering several subsections from barriers to deradicalisation to the characteristics of exit programmes; finally, relevant theoretical and practical conclusions are drawn in section 3.

Conceptual distinction of key terms

A useful distinction between related key concepts shall be made before proceeding with the report. This work will help us clarify what we are referring to when using different concepts such as deradicalisation, disengagement, counter-radicalisation or demobilisation. In the literature, one can find references to terms such as disengagement, countering violent extremism, counter-radicalisation, among others. But what distinguishes one from another? Let’s see what separates deradicalisation from the related concepts.

Deradicalisation

Firstly, how has deradicalisation been conceptualised in the literature?

According to the first report of the United Nation’s Counter-Terrorism Implementation Task Force, the term deradicalisation “is used to refer to programmes that are generally directed against individuals who have become radical with the aim of re-integrating them into society or at least dissuading them from violence” (2008, p. 5).

In his book *Walking away from terrorism: accounts of disengagement from radical and extremist movements*, prominent author John Horgan defines deradicalisation as “the social and

psychological process whereby an individual's commitment to, and involvement in, violent radicalisation is reduced to the extent that they are no longer at risk of involvement and engagement in violent activity" (Horgan, 2009, p. 153).

In a RAND report, deradicalisation is defined as “the process of changing an individual’s belief system, rejecting the extremist ideology, and embracing mainstream values” (Rabasa, Pettyjohn, Ghez, & Boucek, 2010, p. XIII).

On a similar vein, Altier, Thoroughgood, and Horgan (2014) define deradicalisation as “the elimination of one’s belief in a violent, extremist ideology” (p. 647).

The glossary of radicalisation from the European Eye on Radicalisation¹, defines deradicalisation as a process that “aims to delegitimise the use of violence to achieve political goals. Many deradicalised individuals will still hold misogynist, homophobic, xenophobic and anti-democratic views, but they will no longer be a physical threat to society.”

Lastly, an interesting option when defining deradicalisation is by seeing it as the opposite of radicalisation. As stated by Demant, Sloodman, Buijs, and Tillie (2008) deradicalisation “is the process of becoming less radical. This process of ‘becoming less radical’ applies both to behaviour and beliefs. With regard to behaviour, this primarily involves the cessation of violent actions. Regarding beliefs, this involves an increase in confidence in the system, a desire to once more be a part of society, and the rejection of non-democratic means” (p. 13).

According to the multiple definitions that were reached (e.g., Demant et al., 2008; Neumann, 2013), one can add that deradicalisation processes can be of individual or collective nature.

Counter-radicalisation

According to a United Nations (UN) report, “counter-radicalisation refers to policies and programmes aimed at addressing some of the conditions that may propel some individuals down the path of terrorism. It is used broadly to refer to a package of social, political, legal, educational and economic programmes specifically designed to deter disaffected (and possibly already radicalised) individuals from crossing the line and becoming terrorists” (UN, p. 5).

In order to frame *counter-radicalisation strategies* in counter-violent extremism, the European Eye on Radicalisation, defines the former as a “specific sets of policies and initiatives designed to prevent radicalisation or to persuade people who have already chosen a radical path to leave it and return to mainstream society. The strategy sets goals, establishes methods, and divides responsibilities among key stakeholders.”

In Vidino and Brandon's (2012) report a counter-radicalisation strategy is defined as “a set of policies and initiatives (whether seeking deradicalisation, disengagement or radicalisation prevention), often enshrined in a centrally-issued document, which sets goals, describes methods and divides responsibilities among entities in order to elaborate a government’s efforts to counter radicalisation” (p. 9).

¹ <https://eeradicalization.com/glossary-of-radicalization/>

Prevention/Counter-violent extremism (P/CVE)

The European Eye on Radicalisation defines *Counter-violent extremism* as “the whole set of strategies designed to counter extremist messages, propaganda, and recruitment. The measures can range from soft to hard and may include message development and communication, civil society initiatives, political action, new legislation, and intelligence and military operations.”

For other authors, CVE is seen “as a policy spectrum” used to refer to “non-coercive attempts to reduce involvement in terrorism” (Harris-Hogan, Barrelle, & Zammit, 2016, p. 6), that can encompass primary, secondary and tertiary interventions.

Disarmament, demobilisation and reintegration (DDR)

The concept of disarmament, demobilisation and reintegration, usually presented conjointly, refers to “facilitating the process whereby armed insurgent groups cease to engage in organised violence and their members are (re-)integrated into (post-conflict) civilian life, thus creating the foundations for economic recovery and development” (Neumann, 2010, pp. 39-40).

Looking at each term, separately, we can say that:

Disarmament refers to “the collection, control and disposal of small arms, ammunition, explosives and light and heavy weapons of combatants and often also of the civilian population. It includes the development of responsible arms management programmes” (UN Department of Peacekeeping Operations [DPKO], 1999, p. 15).

Demobilisation can be defined as the “process by which armed forces (...) either downsize or completely disband, as part of a broader transformation from war to peace” (DPKO, 1999, p. 15). Reintegration programmes can be described as “assistance measures provided to former combatants that would increase the potential for their and their families’, economic and social reintegration into civil society” (DPKO, 1999, p. 15).

Disengagement

The concept of disengagement is the closest concept to deradicalisation, being sometimes misused interchangeably. However, a clear distinction can be found in the literature, looking at different definitions of disengagement.

Rabasa and colleagues (2010) state that “disengagement entails a change in behaviour (i.e., refraining from violence and withdrawing from a radical organisation) but not necessarily a change in beliefs” (p. XIII). In Vidino and Brandon’s (2012) words, disengagement “entails a less dramatic shift whereby an individual abandons involvement in a terrorist group or activities while perhaps retaining a radical worldview” (p. 9). For other authors, disengagement can be described “as the process of ceasing terrorist activity” (e.g., Altier et al., 2014, p. 648).

Exit programmes

After clarifying the concept of deradicalisation and other similar terms, we now want to present

a definition of exit programmes. But before moving to the definition of exit programmes, since they are intervention programmes it is useful to briefly define what is an intervention programme. In generic terms, an intervention programme comprises a set of methods and strategies employed by a trained professional aiming at producing behavioural changes to improve the status of a person/group/population. That being said, an exit programme/intervention, according to the Radicalisation Awareness Network (RAN, 2018), refers to programmes/intervention strategies aiming at promoting deradicalisation and disengagement. These programmes can target people at different radicalisation stages, including programmes run in prisons that aim to improve inmates' social reintegration. As stated by Bovenkerk (2011), exit programmes were first implemented in the 80's in Italy, and in mid-90's were already being implemented in Germany, The Netherlands, Norway and Sweden, targeting right-wing radicals. In line with the definition already presented, the author makes it clear that in these programmes "it is not enough to get them to refrain from committing acts of terrorism, they have to be totally deradicalised and develop a new identity, the identity of an ex-terrorist" (p. 272), which implies that exit programmes aim at both disengage and deradicalise individuals. Moreover, according to other definitions, exit programmes also encompass rehabilitation and reintegration (Gielen, 2018; Horgan & Braddock, 2010). Therefore, the current deliverable - as well as the work developed under WayOut project - will consider exit programmes as intervention programmes aiming to (Bovenkerk, 2011; Gielen, 2017, 2018; Horgan & Braddock, 2010; Wormith et al., 2007):

1. *Deradicalise* individuals, that is, programmes that work on the cognitive aspects of the radicalised person, aiming at changing the current radical beliefs structure;
2. *Disengage* individuals, that is, programmes which primary goal is to help individuals refrain from (behavioural) violent radicalism;
3. *Rehabilitation*, that is, programmes that provide a broad array of psychosocial interventions and services that aim to address inmates' needs; and
4. *Reintegration*, that is, programmes aiming at helping individuals return to communities successfully, providing a network of social support to help the (former) radicalised individual in his/her reintegration and return to previous roles in society.

These programmes can be implemented at different stages, namely at pre and post-imprisonment and during incarceration (Gielen, 2018). Despite the fact that programmes can have the abovementioned aims, one should state that **programmes should have a clear set of goals defined and focus its intervention strategy on deradicalisation or disengagement, in order to be considered an exit programme**. A focus on reintegration and rehabilitation should be part of the programmes as it represents an important aspect of intervention programmes. Focus on reintegration and rehabilitation is particularly important if we consider programmes run during probation. Considering the multiple approaches, actors involved and importance given to the ideological component, Koehler (2017) considers seven types of programmes:

- a) Non-governmental programmes with a passive approach that target ideological component;
- b) Non-governmental programmes with a passive approach without ideological component;
- c) Non-governmental programmes with an active approach with some ideological component;
- d) Governmental programmes with an active approach with ideological component;
- e) Governmental programmes with an active approach without ideological component;
- f) Governmental programmes with a passive approach with some ideological component;
- g) Programmes run by both governmental and non-governmental actors (public-private partnerships with a passive approach and targeting ideological component.

In sum, deradicalisation generally refers to an individual or collective cognitive change characterised by the rejection of violent action to achieve political/religious goals and former (rigid) ideology. Therefore, it is different from counter-radicalisation and counter violent extremism, that are broader terms that refer to strategies and policy initiatives to tackle radicalisation (these strategies may include prevention of radicalisation, intervention with individuals in danger of radicalisation, and deradicalisation) (Korn, 2016), and from disengagement, that stands for a behavioural change (e.g., abandon of terrorist action/activities/movement) that can lead to (but not necessarily includes) deradicalisation (i.e., the needed cognitive change). Going a bit further on the later distinction (i.e., deradicalisation vs disengagement), research suggests that disengagement from terrorism without (cognitive) deradicalisation may be the rule and not the exception, meaning that deradicalisation is at the end of a long journey that starts with declarative disengagement - a commitment to stop using violence -, followed by behavioural disengagement and organisational disengagement - leaving the group (Schmid, 2013).

Disarmament, demobilisation and reintegration (DDR) are concepts more related with war than with terrorism. However, disengagement can involve a disarmament step. Reintegration is also part of both disengagement and deradicalisation, however the assistance measures are not the same when compared to (legal) armed forces that were involved in a war.

Going further in the distinction between deradicalisation and disengagement, it can be said that these concepts have their root in two different approaches. As stated by Neumann (2013), different historical experiences and philosophical traditions led to what the author labelled as the “Anglo-Saxon” and the “European” approach. The former is mostly concerned with behavioural radicalisation and the intervention of authorities starts when there is an intention to break the law (therefore closely connected with the disengagement approach, where a guarantee of no more violence is enough). On other hand, the European approach, while aiming to tackle both cognitive and behavioural radicalisation, puts more emphasis on cognitive radicalisation, seeing extremist ideas on their own as problematic (closer to the approach of deradicalisation programmes, where changes in the cognitive aspects are required for success). This fundamental difference between the two approaches raises some criticism of both. The Anglo-Saxon approach, while being better in the short-term (i.e., dealing more efficiently with security threats), lacks a long-term impact, since the cognitive aspects that can led to terrorist activities are not dealt with. The European approach is sometimes considered to be an obstacle to individuals’ freedom of speech or even anti-democratic.

Considering these criticisms, and to avoid the freedom of speech argument (that encompasses a violation of a fundamental constitutional right in democratic societies), we argue that exit programmes with deradicalisation goals should only be implemented on a voluntary basis.

Before moving to the theoretical and practical development on exit strategies, let’s have a look on the determinants of radicalisation.

Overview on the determinants of radicalisation

Although the focus of this report is on deradicalisation and exit strategies, it is important to understand the determinants of radicalisation and to define them. Scientific literature has pointed

out risk factors at different levels and determinants such as age, gender, emotional vulnerability, mental health, dissatisfaction with current activity, identification with victims, violence as an acceptable mean to achieve political/religious goals, sense of reward about joining the terrorist organisation, family or kinship relations with terrorists, perceived illegitimacy of authorities, perceived in-group superiority, distance to other people and societal disconnection (Doosje, Loseman, & van den Bos, 2013; Horgan, 2008; Monahan, 2012; van San, 2015). Even though individual resilience to processes of radicalisation remains a neglected area of research, a combination of the mentioned determinants/risk factors may lead to radicalisation. Radicalisation has been conceptualised as having a cognitive and behavioural/violent component. The cognitive aspects can be described as “the process through which an individual adopts ideas that are severely at odds with those of the mainstream, refutes the legitimacy of the existing social order, and seeks to replace it with a new structure based on a completely different belief system” (Vidino & Brandon, 2012, p. 9). On the other hand, the behavioural component of (violent) radicalisation “occurs when an individual takes the additional step of employing violence to further the views derived from cognitive radicalism” (Vidino & Brandon, 2012, p. 9).

Doosje and Eerten (2017) presented a model of radicalisation and deradicalisation that can help us considering different risk factors at different levels. The authors state we have a shield of resilience against radical influences that can be threatened by personal, group level and societal factors (or micro, meso, and macro factors in the authors’ nomenclature). Once these factors pass the shield, the radicalisation process encompasses three phases: (1) a sensitivity phase, (2) a group membership phase and (3) an action phase. The sensitivity phase is the one where a susceptible person may still be open to counter-or alternative narrative campaigns, since once radicalised another shield of resilience must be overcome for deradicalisation to occur. This new shield needs to be surpassed in order to allow the deradicalisation of the individual. This model is interesting in that it argues that radicalisation and deradicalisation can be explained in the same model, or, in Bertram (2015) words, “to understand how a terrorist may be deradicalised, we must consider what circumstantial factors lead to a given terrorist being radicalised in the first place” (p. 121). However, deradicalisation is not simply the reverse process of radicalisation since additional factors will play an important role after the person becomes radicalised.

Another model of radicalisation/deradicalisation, usually called the Quest for Significance Model, was developed by Kruglanski et al. (2014). The authors consider the following three components:

- Motivational component related with a universal human motivation - quest for significance. This first component explains the radicalisation process as being motivated by a quest for significance, that is, a desire to matter, to be someone. Therefore, a perceived loss of significance (through deprivation or avoidance) or a perceived opportunity to significance gain (incentive) activate the quest for significance;
- Ideological component. Represents, in this model, the means to achieve a desired goal. Ideology identifies the means (violence, terrorist activity) to achieve the goal of personal significance;
- Social processes by which individuals contacts with, share and strengthen the ideology.

All components will contribute to see violence as an acceptable mean to achieve the significance goal leading to radicalisation at the individual level (the model considers the phases of passive support, active support, participation and self-sacrifice) and groups level radicalisation.

To better understand the radicalisation process, we will now summarise some of the risk factors presented in the literature.

Starting with the individual risk factors, Table 1 presents the considered risk factors and defines them:

Individual Risk Factor	Definition
ACTIVISM AND RADICALISM	One important indicator of the risk of an individual to join a radicalised group may be his or her level of activism and radicalism. These two different but related components have been measured considering the work of Moskaleiko and McCauley (2009a) (Moskaleiko & McCauley, 2009b), already applied in Spain (Trujillo, Prados, & Moyano, 2016). Activism and radicalism can be distinguished because the first encompasses a legal and non-violent political action, whereas the second represents an illegal and violent action.
PERSONAL SACRIFICE	The level of sacrifice that an individual is willing to suffer in order to support a cause can be an important indicator of radicalisation. Therefore, the self-sacrifice scale (Bélanger, Caouette, Sharvit, & Dugas, 2014) can be an important measure to assess the radicalisation level of a person/inmate. Moreover, we can state that the willingness to sacrifice one's own life is at the end of the radicalisation process, where the individual has already been indoctrinated and is fully committed to the group or with a cause.
SOCIAL DOMINANCE ORIENTATION	The belief that a group (or country, or race, among others) is superior to another is a way to legitimate violent and radical action. The social dominance orientation captures the desire that an individual has for dominance based on group characteristics and inequality. Therefore, the Social Dominance Orientation scale (Pratto, Sidanius, & Levin, 2006) can represent an interesting measure to evaluate the in-group superiority factor.
IDENTITY FUSION AND IDENTIFICATION	It represents two related but different constructs. Identity fusion occurs when someone is so embedded in the group that he or she willing to sacrifice him-or herself for the group. In a different way, identification is related to an alignment with the group's goals and action. The assessment of both constructs can be done with the scale developed by Gómez and colleagues (2011). The problem related with extreme identification/identity fusion is well pointed out by Loza (2007, p. 150), who stated that "terrorists tend to submerge their own identities into the group, resulting in a kind of 'group mind', 'group identity', and 'group moral code' that requires unquestioned obedience to the group". In fact, the said unquestioned obedience can lead vulnerable people who join terrorist groups to commit extreme acts of violence and that justifies the inclusion of identity fusion and identification as a risk factor.
PERSONAL EMOTIONAL	Personal emotional uncertainty represents a (subjective) "sense of

UNCERTAINTY	doubt or instability in self-views, world-views, or the interrelation between the two” (Doosje et al., 2013, p. 589) and can be an antecedent of a radical belief system. Therefore, it can be useful to use available measures to assess the emotional uncertainty (of inmates) like the scale used by Doosje and colleagues (2013) and developed by Greco and Roger (2001).
NEED TO BELONG	The need for belonging, in general (Borum, 2014), or the need to belong to an empowering religion/ideology (Sinai, 2014) represents a psychological vulnerability than can put individuals at risk of being radicalised. Moreover, the need to belong, which is “a need to form and maintain at least a minimum quantity of interpersonal relationships” represents an innate and nearly universal characteristic (Baumeister & Leary, 1995, p. 499) and thus should be present across different situations/life events, cultures, countries and religions. Therefore, it is essential to assess the need to belong, considering that the higher the need the higher the risk. Leary, Kelly, Cottrell, and Schreindorfer (2013) measure represents a valid instrument that can be adapted to evaluate the need to belong.
SELF-ESTEEM	It can be described as “an individual’s global evaluation of his or her overall worth as a person” (Steiger, Allemand, Robins, & Fend, 2014, p. 325). As defended by Sinai (2014), individuals with a low self-esteem can be more vulnerable to radical messages. The same suggestion, that a low self-esteem represents an identifiable trait of terrorists, is made by other scholars (cf. Loza, 2007). This relationship can be related with the more studied one about self-esteem and violent behaviour and aggression (Feddes, Mann, & Doosje, 2015). The low self-esteem hypothesis is a plausible one, considering current research that found that a “curvilinear association between self-esteem and radicalisation; a moderate level of self-esteem is associated with resilience to violent radicalisation while too high levels of self-esteem (narcissism) can make individuals more susceptible to radicalisation” (Feddes et al., 2015, p. 407). Self-esteem, as a classic psychological variable, can be assessed with numerous instruments, of which we highlight Rosenberg’s (1965) instrument.
DISTANCE TO OTHER PEOPLE AND SOCIETAL DISCONNECTION	Distance to other people and societal disconnection were found to be determinants of a radical belief system. This is in line with other risks, such as the need to belong, since the more distanced the person is the more he/she deviates from a basic human need. These variables, representing the individuals’ deviation from the mainstream culture and shared norms, can be assessed with Doosje and colleagues (2013) items, which were adapted in the present proposal for cultural reasons and considering the targeted population.

Table 1 - Individual risk factors for radicalisation

Furthermore, the literature also points out environmental risk factors. Sinai (2014), in his 7-phase

model of radicalisation in prison², considers situational/contextual factors (phase 2), which enable/facilitate the progression of vulnerable individuals in the radicalisation process. According to the author, the most important of these factors are:

- 1) presence of extremist social networks, such as religious-based gangs, that provide the protection, physical and social support that vulnerable prisoners are seeking;
- 2) presence of extremist ideologies;
- 3) presence of charismatic inmate leaders;
- 4) presence of extremist prison chaplains;
- 5) outreach programs by external extremist organisations that distribute extremist materials;
- 6) presence of terrorist ‘kingpins’;
- 7) ‘virtual’ presence by terrorist organisations.

In the community, environmental risk factors (meso level) mentioned in the literature and that can be key to exit programmes in probation include fraternal relative deprivation (i.e., a sense that other groups are treated better than the group we identify with) and influence from friendship and relatives (Doosje et al., 2016; Sageman, 2004).

In sum, although the focus of this report is centred in deradicalisation, it is important to know and describe the radicalisation risk factors presented in the literature, both at the individual and contextual levels. This is so because the risk factors that led to radicalisation can be used in deradicalisation programmes, meaning that we can look at each factor and develop some strategies to support the individuals, that can be included in deradicalisation programmes, thus mitigating the identified risk(s).

² Sinai’s model considers the following seven phases of inmates’ radicalisation: (1) Pre-radicalisation personal factors; (2) Situational/contextual factors and enablers; (3) Self-identification; (4) Indoctrination; (5) Militancy; (6) Post-prison release terrorism; and (7) Post-attack re-incarceration.

2. Theoretical and practical developments on exit programmes

Literature in the field of deradicalisation has been growing in the last decade, exploring and clarifying the factors that made terrorists stay or leave the group. This is understandable because it was since the outbreak of the Syrian Civil War that European countries increased their awareness regarding foreign fighters that joined terrorist organisations, such as Daesh³. This section aims to present, from a theoretical and practical perspective, studies that allow us to identify relevant contributions in the field of exit strategies.

2.1 Barriers to deradicalisation and the push and pull factors

One thing seems to be hard to rebut: the previous destruction of relationships and abandonment of significant groups makes it hard for the person to leave a terrorist organisation, since “the activist has nowhere to go” (Noricks, 2009, p. 302), fears reprisals that may occur from the inner group and may lack the needed protection against (former) enemy groups. Other barriers to deradicalisation mentioned in the literature include social and psychological dependency and marginal position following deradicalisation (Demant et al., 2008). Moreover, the radical has a shield that makes him/her “less likely to be persuaded by anti-radical messages from outside their group” (Doosje et al., 2016, p. 82).

2.1.1. Pull factors

Noricks' (2009) chapter on disengagement and deradicalisation argues that a key pull factor (factors that represent a shift in a terrorist's priorities) that was missing in the literature is the importance of alternative social networks that will work as a receiving group to the former extremist. Other pull factors include the desire for a normal life, the desire to establish family/parental/spousal roles, new employment or educational opportunities, new role models or social group(s), a more compelling ideology or belief structure, financial incentives, positive interactions with moderate people, and employment or educational demands or opportunities (Altier et al., 2014; Noricks, 2009). Relationships (particularly with relatives, children and spouses) have been pointed out as the most prominent pull factor leading to exit (Windisch, Simi, Ligon, & McNeel, 2016), reinforcing the positive role that families can have during this process. The review done by Altier et al. (2014) sheds light on the importance of pull factors, such as financial incentives and the attraction for new roles, later on the exit programme, supporting the participants' successful reintegration.

Exploring different disengagement patterns for 4 terrorist organisations (ETA, Islamic State, The Red Hand Commando, and Ulster Volunteer Force), Palm (2017) found common pull factors mentioned by former members such as “getting older, finding space to think, fear, boredom, spiritual experiences, family members killed by the group, being shocked by one's own actions and being homesick” (p. 104) and time for reflection while in prison.

2.1.2. Push factors

³ Can also be referred to as ISIS (Islamic State of Iraq and Syria), ISIL (Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant) or IS (Islamic State).

Still in the push/pull framework, push factors for deradicalisation, that is, “aspects related to individuals’ experiences while involved in terrorism that drive them away” (Altier et al., 2014, p. 648), include: unmet expectations; disillusionment with strategy/actions of terrorist group; disillusionment with personnel; difficulty adapting to clandestine lifestyle; inability to cope with physiological/psychological effects of violence; loss of faith in ideology; and burnout. Analysing 87 autobiographical accounts of disengaged individuals, Altier, Boyle, Shortland, and Horgan’s (2017) findings show that “push factors are more likely to be experienced by those who choose to walk away from terrorism and are more likely to be reported as playing a role in their exit decisions than pull factors” (p.320), with disillusion with group actions and strategy being the most prevalent disengagement factor. Similar factors are highlighted by Jacobson’s (2010) report, such as the disagreement with group’s ideological direction, grievances with leaders, (positive) family interventions, and contradictions between what the person expected about what being a terrorist would be like and what it actually is. Windisch, Simi, Ligon, and McNeel (2016) also found disillusionment as a common theme in disengagement studies.

2.2 Disengagement and deradicalisation factors

Analysing 58 public testimonials of Islamic State defectors, Neumann (2015) found four narratives supporting members’ disengagement: (1) infighting: this narrative is related to the IS actions against Sunni Muslims, viewed as “wrong, counterproductive and religiously illegitimate” (p. 10) by the defectors; (2) atrocities against Sunni Muslims as well as killing of innocent civilians; (3) corruption and un-Islamic behaviours: commanders behaviour with fighters as well as IS behaviours not aligned with what the group stands for form this narrative; (4) quality of life: this narrative encompasses testimonials related with harsh life conditions, not aligned with what was promised during the recruitment stage.

Demant and colleagues (2008) developed a qualitative study in the Netherlands in which they interviewed former radicals from different groups such as the Mollucans, left and right-wing radicals, and Islamists. They described motives related with deradicalisation/disengagement linked to ideology, organisation, and practical circumstances and reached the following conclusions:

1. Rejection of violence plays a key role in deradicalisation. This rejection can have an ideological, strategic or organisational nature;
2. Realisation that the groups’ vision is not achievable;
3. Society is no longer seen as the enemy, meaning that the person realises he/she as part of the society;
4. Disappointment related with little group influence or lifestyle;
5. Practical life circumstances, such as responsibilities and wishing to establish their own life, and particularly negative variants (such as stigmatisation, outside pressure and isolation) leverage deradicalisation; and
6. Significant others (whose opinion matters to the radical).

Other authors have highlighted deradicalisation factors such as: (1) rejection of rigid ideology/loss of ideological appeal (Doosje et al., 2016; Pressman, 2009); (2) rejection of violence; (3) evidence of replacement of non-violent goals; (4) presence of motivation to deradicalise; (5) presence of community support; (6) prison sentence, since it can create the conditions for a new start (Doosje et al., 2016). On the other hand, disengagement factors have also been underlined, namely: (1)

belief that violence is a failing strategy; (2) disillusionment with spiritual leadership; (3) shift in ideology; (4) disillusionment with organisation experiences; (5) growing away from the movement (Pressman, 2009).

2.3 Psychological theories

Moving beyond the push/pull factors, the investment model, proposed by Rusbult (1980; Rusbult & Farrell, 1983), that has been applied in different fields (such as relationships or turnover intentions), can also be an important theoretical model to understand the disengagement process. According to this model, ones' probability to remain in a given group depends on the commitment one has to the group and how psychologically bounded with a group a given person is. Commitment itself, in turn, depends on three factors:

- Satisfaction: how positively the member evaluates the group;
- Alternatives: when only poor alternatives are available, one tends to be more committed to the current group;
- Investment size: when one is heavily invested in involvement in a group, one is more committed.

Therefore, when someone positively evaluates the group he/she belongs to, and with the lack of alternatives, and when the person is heavily invested in the group, commitment is expected to be high. On the other hand, if someone is unsatisfied with the group, sees better alternatives, and did not invest a lot in the group, it is easier to abandon the group, since the commitment levels will be low. Moreover, practical implications can be drawn from this model, considering that, at least, intervention programmes can try to create alternatives to the radicals' current situation.

Other psychological theories have been applied to this field, helping us understand why people that reached a certain level of extremism may reject (showing negative feelings) counter-attitudinal messages that focus on attitudes, feelings and behaviours that are important to the person. This fundamental aversion against dissonant themes is known as *cognitive dissonance* (Festinger, 1957). In other words, when two relevant cognitions are not consistent (e.g., smoking and knowing that smoking is bad for your health), people experience discomfort and unpleasant (mental) tension (i.e., cognitive dissonance), thus acting in order to reduce this dissonance (e.g., avoiding inconsistent messages; changing behaviours). This particular theory, in the view of Dalgaard-Nielsen (2013), helps explain why the radical individual approached by an exit programme “will be highly resistant to embark on the supposedly rather fundamental cognitive revisions required” (p. 107). Therefore, following the cited authors statement, we can argue that an active approach will encounter high resistance from the potential participants. Exploring the impact of this theory in the field of online counter-narrative campaigns, van Eerten, Doosje, Konijn, and Goede (2017) also state that “those undertaking counter-narrative efforts will have a hard time influencing those who have invested heavily in extremists groups and ideology” (p. 35).

Another theory that has been linked to the deradicalisation programmes is Brehm's (1966) *reactance theory*, that affirms people try to “protect their freedom to think, act, and believe as they like” (Dalgaard-Nielsen, 2013, p. 107). Therefore, external influences to change beliefs, attitudes and behaviours will be viewed as freedom-threatening and the person will naturally resist such influence attempts (Dalgaard-Nielsen, 2013; van Eerten et al., 2017), reinforcing the need for voluntary participation in exit programmes.

Social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; 1986 *cit in* Van Eerten et al., 2017) and *self-categorisation theory* (Turner, Hogg, Oakes, Reicher, & Wetherell, 1987 *cit in* Van Eerten et al., 2017) also help us to understand the challenges involved in countering-radicalisation through counter-narratives. In sum, social-identity theory postulates that our self-concept incorporates social identities from our group memberships. The stronger the identification with a group, the higher the tendency to be biased against outgroup messages. As the self-categorisation theory states, when a strong social identity is present, people tend to “perceive themselves and others less as unique individuals, and more in terms of our group memberships” (van Eerten et al., 2017, p. 40). Thus, intervention programmes need to consider the relevance of groups in participants’ self-concept, including phases related with the construction of a new healthy social identity, apart from previous radicalised worldviews shared by the participant.

In sum, these theories have implications for exit programmes, namely these programmes should be as subtle as possible in order not to activate the natural resistances of the potential *exiteer*. Moreover, one must invest heavily in the relationship with the participant/client, increasing the person’s feeling of safety and willingness to receive messages that are not coherent with his/her worldviews.

2.4 Relevant theories from other fields

Other theoretical contributions came from the field of desistance from crime and can provide useful insights to the field of exit programmes. Namely, Maguire (2007) argues in favour of a set of principles, that should be aligned with offenders’ circumstances, and that should guide interventions, such as:

- a) Agency (i.e., the individuals’ capacity to act independently and to make their own free choices) is as important as - if not more important than - structure in promoting or inhibiting desistance from crime;
- b) Individuals differ in their readiness to contemplate and begin the process of change;
- c) Generating and sustaining motivation is vital to the maintenance of processes of change;
- d) Desistance is a difficult and often lengthy process, not an ‘event’, and relapses are common;
- e) While overcoming social problems is often insufficient on its own to promote desistance, it may be a necessary condition for further progress;
- f) As people change, they need new skills and capacities appropriate to their new lifestyle, and access to opportunities to use them.

From this set of principles related with desistance from crime we can say that exit programmes should have a social service and counselling component, working with the offenders’ motivation for the process of change and helping the person in the development of new skills.

2.5 Exit programmes: characteristics, implementation and lessons learned

Regarding **exit programmes**, they come into play when the person is already radicalised but is willing to engage in an intervention programme because there is an available programme that is appealing to the person and/or the programme provides a pack of incentives that encourages participation. Therefore, these intervention programmes, implemented on a voluntary basis, aim

to “besides (re)integration into society (...) to confront the ideological interpretation regime, because the decision to exit is only the start of a long detachment process from previous thought patterns” (Korn, 2016, p. 183).

The question of voluntary vs involuntary participation in programmes developed in prison settings has been scarcely addressed in the literature. However, a study in the U.S. with 100 participants (of which 60 were involuntary) admitted on a substance abuse treatment programme, concluded that regardless of the admission status (voluntary vs involuntary), inmates showed significant changes in the measured psychological functioning variables (e.g., depression, self-esteem, decision making) and no group differences were found in other outcomes (i.e., whether the inmate paroled from the programme or was discharged from the programme; whether inmates were referred to aftercare, community-based programme) (Prendergast, Farabee, Cartier, & Henkin, 2002).

But how voluntary are inmates’ participation in intervention programmes? The Cambridge dictionary defines voluntary as “done, made, or given willingly, without being forced or paid to do it”. However, we can argue that the concept of voluntary participation is much more problematic in a prison setting, considering the power asymmetry between staff and inmates as well as the potential consequences related with non-participation in prison activities and programmes.

Box 1 - Voluntary vs involuntary participation

An experimental approach to deradicalisation, with a strong focus on the radicalised person’s cognitions and emotions was developed and implemented in France (Bouzar & Martin, 2016). Build upon the cognitive theory that connects emotions, cognitions and behaviours, the approach is based on three phases:

- 1) Phase 1 - Emotional approach: during this first stage, it is important for the professional to search for a trusty ally that has a strong bond with the radicalised person. It can be a teacher, educator, or family member. With the help of this tutor, the professional will learn about the radicalised person’s history and reasons for commitment (i.e., quest for significance). After this initial step, the tutor should contact the radicalised individual and evoke long-term autobiographic memories that have a potential to stir up emotions that set the person apart from the deindividuation promoted by the radical group. The main idea at this first phase is to connect individually with a radicalised individual that may be diluted in a strong group identity;
- 2) Phase 2 - Cognitive approach: at this stage, the aim is to open a cognitive window to question the rigid ideological beliefs the radicalised person now has. The contribution of a former radicalised individual is welcomed, providing the radicalised individual with alternative paths and giving him/her new information. Moreover, the testimony of a former radicalised person can create a mirror effect for the radicalized individual.
- 3) Phase 3 - Cognitive restructuring: the third and last stage is the longest one, since after

the emotional approach that allows for a connection with the radicalised individual, and the cognitive approach that deconstructed the radicalised individual's beliefs, the radicalised individual will likely face a hard period marked by uncertainty, questioning his or her current and past choices. It is key that during this stage the radicalised individual understands his or her previous vulnerabilities and creates positive resources that will allow him or her to face the current uncertainties without depending on the extremist group.

According to the authors, the time needed to run the programme depends on the participants age and initial level of radicalisation. The most difficult aspects are related with relational issues and group membership rather than ideology. This approach was implemented by the “Centre de prévention des dérives sectaires liées à l'Islam” (CPDSI) in France, financed by the French Ministry of Internal Affairs - Ministère de l'Intérieur (2014-2016). However, despite the CPDSI claiming a success rate of 86% considering 809 pro-jihadist youths involved in the programme, these results were received with scepticism. In fact, other practitioners consider that such a high success rate with this number of participants cannot be achieved in this small timespan⁴.

Reviewing available deradicalisation programmes, namely the exit programmes in Europe (Scandinavia and Germany) and Asia (Saudi Arabia, Yemen, Singapore, and Indonesia), Dechesne (2011) summarised its findings in the following propositions:

- Programmes targeting right-wing extremists are mostly disengagement programmes, since they target behavioural aspects of involvement with the radical organisation;
- There aren't enough insights into what leads people to deradicalise;
- Insights from social cognition (psychology) are insufficiently used to increase programmes' effectiveness.

In another literature review about leaving criminal organisations, Bovenkerk (2011) reached four main conclusions:

1. “For practical reasons it is more logical to try and discourage prospective perpetrators from acts of violence than to try and ideologically deradicalise them” (p. 274). In other words, one can say that a disengagement approach is more practical than a deradicalisation one, considering the difference between cease terrorist activity and the cognitive restructuring needed to deradicalise an individual;
2. In most cases, deradicalisation is a spontaneous process that comes with age, wisdom and adoption of conventional rules;
3. “State policy can be supported by special exit programs” (p. 274); however, these programmes' effectiveness needs to be evaluated;
4. The need for more robust behavioural interventions to deal with the relationship between negative social capital⁵ and membership in criminal organisations, that is, interventions that aim to increase the social capital of criminals.

In practice, exit programmes have been implemented in several countries. As Noricks (2009) stated, ten years ago programmes were already being implemented in “Egypt, Yemen, Saudi

⁴ Cf. https://www.lepoint.fr/societe/deradicalisation-les-resultats-de-dounia-bouzar-sont-ils-credibles-26-06-2017-2138413_23.php

⁵ Negative social capital refers to the negative consequences that can emerge from sociability (cf. Portes, 2009).

Arabia, Jordan, Algeria, Tajikistan, Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, and the United Kingdom (UK)” (p. 306). Most programmes work in three main pillars:

- 1) Reinterpretation of ideology (aiming at delegitimising the use of violence against others; usually a theological component - In the case of religious extremists);
- 2) Social service; and
- 3) Individual counselling/psychological component⁶.

Dean (2012), based on his experience in the implementation of the prevent strategy in the UK stated that to encourage inmates’ disengagement from terrorism, interventions should target the following goals:

1. Enable inmate to meet personal needs and desires that do not involve the connection with an extremist group, cause or ideology;
2. Address the specific attitudes or beliefs that enable inmates to harm others directly or indirectly (supporting others);
3. Enabling inmates to “express, tolerate and cope with powerful emotions without denigrating or harming others” (p. 32);
4. Empower inmates to “take more responsibility for who they are, how they live their lives and the personal commitments they make” (p. 32);
5. Encourage inmates to pursue their goals using alternatives that do not involve breaking the law or causing harm to others.

In the United States, Parker (2013) developed a thesis where the author presents four proactive measures to provide treatment for radicalised inmates, namely:

- Counselling programme (voluntary and cognitive based) for convicted terrorists and radical inmates;
- Pack of incentives (e.g., sentence reduction, aftercare programmes) for inmates participating in the deradicalisation programme;
- Strict recruitment of professional (psychologists, chaplains, and volunteers) that will deliver the counselling programme;
- Ensure an aftercare monitoring/supervision, counselling and social service assistance.

Webber and colleagues (2018) research in Sri Lanka assessed the effectiveness of the rehabilitation programme developed to deradicalise former members of the “Liberation Tigers of Tamil Eelam” group in specific rehabilitation centres. The authors measured dimensions such as embeddedness (of the participants in the social structure of the group), attitudes towards deradicalisation, loss of significance in beneficiaries of the rehabilitation programme that completed the program and others who received minimal treatment. The author concluded that “beneficiaries receiving full rehabilitation reported increasingly lower extremism across one year and showed greater reduction than those only receiving minimal treatment” (p. 551). This provides some evidence regarding this intervention’s effectiveness. Moreover, considering that sentences for this inmates’ group are typically short, it is important to consider that intervention programmes should have a post-incarceration continuance and monitoring stages to ensure its effectiveness.

⁶ This is the key component of the programme run in Saudi Arabia government in prisons, started in 2004, comprises a six-week course on topics such as “loyalty, allegiance, terrorism and even self-esteem” (Noricks, 2009, p. 307), and involves people arrested for sympathy or minor infractions related with terrorism or radical ideological groups, not the ones arrested for terrorist acts.

The author also proposes that deradicalisation “should contain two critical elements: promoting inner openness for a change of mind and presenting alternative views from the outside” (p. 291).

Therefore, the reviewed literature provides a set of knowledge that allow us to better understand how exit programmes work, not only from a theoretical perspective but also from practical knowledge gained from the implementation of these programmes.

3. Conclusions

The current literature review aimed at defining deradicalisation as well as separating this concept from other relevant ones. Moreover, it aimed to provide an up-to-date overview of the theoretical and practical literature on exit programmes - defined as intervention programmes primarily aiming at deradicalise and/or disengage participants, but that can also encompass rehabilitation and reintegration goals.

From the first goal, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Deradicalisation can be defined as an individual or collective cognitive change characterised by the rejection of violent action to achieve political/religious goals and former (rigid) ideology;
- Disengagement and deradicalisation are conceptually close topics but disengagement often occurs first and is characterised by the abandonment of violent action to achieve political/religious goals but does not necessarily incorporates the rejection of radical ideologies.

From the theoretical and practical development on exit programmes, we can conclude that:

- Exit programmes are intervention programmes that mostly aim to disengage and deradicalise individuals. Frequently, these programmes also have rehabilitation and reintegration goals;
- Exit programmes usually incorporate an ideological component, a social service component and an individual counselling/psychological component;
- Theories from psychology and sociology can help us understand why individuals engage in radical groups and how can they exit those organisations.
- Push factors such as disillusionment with group activities/actions are important disengagement factors, with a stronger influence than pull factors.

The work developed and the contributions from partners with different backgrounds (ranging from Universities to organisations implementing exit interventions) led us to a reflection about differences between what makes sense from a theoretical and practical perspective. For instance, while theoretically deradicalisation and disengagement can be clearly distinguished, in practice ideological (deradicalisation) work seems to be needed in order to achieve successful disengagement. Thus, the clear theoretical distinction between these concepts appears more blurred from a practical perspective, since aspects of both dimensions need to be worked together.

Therefore, the present work contributes with the needed knowledge that will be key in the following WayOut deliverables. That is, in order to map the existing exit programmes in prison and probation we first need to clarify and define some key terms, as was made in this report. Moreover, knowing the theories behind the programmes will be crucial to draw a proposal for programmes' evaluation and be able to effectively evaluate them.

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